

New Business Opportunities for E-Commerce: Post Lockdown

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Abstract: E-commerce (electronic commerce) is that the activity of electronically buying or selling of products on online services or over the web. E-commerce draws on technologies like mobile commerce, electronic funds transfer, supply chain management; Internet marketing, online transaction processing, electronic data interchange (EDI), inventory management systems, and automatic data collection systems. E-commerce is successively driven by the technological advances of the semiconductor industry, and is that the largest sector of the industry. E-commerce typically uses the online for in any case a neighborhood of a transaction's life cycle although it's going to also use other technologies like e-mail. Typical e-commerce transactions include the acquisition of products (such as books from Amazon) or services (such as music downloads within the sort of digital distribution like iTunes Store. There are three areas of e-commerce: online retailing, electronic markets, and online auctions. E-commerce is supported by electronic business. Electronic commerce or e-commerce (sometimes written as E -Commerce) is a business model that lets firms and individuals buy and sell things over the internet. E-commerce operates in all four of the following major market segments: Business to Business, Business to Consumer, Consumer to Consumer, Consumer to Business.

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1. Introduction

Electronic Commerce (E-Commerce) emerged in early 90s. It is the activity of buying and selling tangible and intangible products, transmission of data and funds through electronic mode. E-commerce can be conducted over smart phone, tablet or computer. The E-Commerce market size is valued at USD 9.09 trillion globally and it is expected that it will grow at a compound annual growth rate of 14.7% from 2020 to 2027. Indian is the fastest growing E-Commerce market and is expected to grow at approximately 1200% by 2026. Also Indian E-Commerce market is expected to reach \$84 billion by 2021. The ever-expanding users of 3G/4G are changing the business scenario in India as it grew by 10% in 2018. Indian accounts for almost more than 10% of the smart-phone market globally. E-Commerce is helping the businesses in establishing a wider market by providing more efficient and cheaper distribution channels.

2. Changing market scenario Post Lockdown

In 2020 due to COVID-19 pandemic there are lot many changes occurring in the traditional markets and online markets also. Scope for online selling has been increased many folds. Work from Home' culture is making its way all around the world. Due to these opportunities provided by institutions/businesses people are habitual of online working. Now they understand the benefits of online work culture, online buying and selling better than earlier.

3. Scope for Services

If you observe the E-Commerce market closely; you will see that till today garments, footwear, fashion products, electronics, mobile phones, computers and laptops are being sold heavily through E-Commerce. These all are tangible products which can be sold or bought by showing the pictures, videos and graphics of the product features. Very fewer services are being sold online. Now during Covid-19 we saw that people are trying to buy all the tangibles as well as intangibles online to avoid going out. Everybody is worried about the health of the family. Kids and older people are more prone to this pandemic. So this is great time for the service providers to convert this fear into business opportunity. Though earlier also many services are being provided online; but not gained much success till now due to their feature of intangibility. But now people have gained experience of using making services online. The following services can be successfully provided online:

- Astrology
- Career counseling services
- Professional and short term courses

- Services by the psychiatrist
- Architecture services
- Services of Accountant and auditors
- Online coaching and tuition

For some of these services detail is given below:

- **Astrology**

Astrology is all about linking the 12 zodiac signs to planets and stars to manage life on earth. Collins Dictionary defines astrology as the movement of planets, stars, sun and moon in the belief that these movements influence the lives of the people. Astrology was earlier devised in the Middle East Greece and transmitted to 21st century by the Islamic world. These days Horoscope and Astrology columns are a common feature of newspapers, women`s magazines and the web these days. Research shows that around 90% people know about Zodiac signs. In India great number of people believes in astrology, numerology, tarot card reading etc. In our country, till now people are visiting astrologer physically; taking hard copies of their Kundli to discuss their good and bad destiny. Earlier astrologers were making kundlis at their own; but now many astrologers have started making kundlis with the help of computer software. There are many websites which are in business of online astrology; but not much people are turning up as our people believe in face to face discussion more. But now Covid-19 has opened the doors of success for this business online. These days`people are not going out much. They avoid meeting people, exchanging things and close contacts. So this is right time to shift people from physically visiting to an online video call to the desired astrologers while saving the travel time, wait time and energy. Following Model can be followed for running the successful online astrology business: Designing a Website Registration of various Astrologers-Sign-up by the client & choosing the Astrologer by seeing their Profile Choosing the service Mode (Through SMS, Video call, Voice call, E-mail) Choosing depth of service (full reading or particular question) Making the Online Payment, Payment is received by the host Forwarding the clients request to the chosen Astrologer SMS/Call/Video call by the Astrologer within 10-15 Minutes Discussion & Feedback.

- **Career Counseling Services**

These days there is cut-through competition in every face of life. In all the courses and degree students have to go through long procedures of entrance test and interviews. Also they are confused while choosing the career path. Any of them are sure about their interests and strength They just choose the

path whatever is chosen by the parents for them or the follow their friends/siblings. But many times they fail due to loss of interest in the chosen subject/career path. So in today`s era where lot number of options are available with everyone; it becomes really vital to choose right career or subjects to be followed in future. In every school/college/University career counselor are available to guide the students as per their interests. But there are chances of biasness if we go to counselors who are a part of particular institute because they bound to promote their own institute courses. So there is need of free lancers who can guide honestly. But sometimes people are not able to visit free lancers due to time, money or some other constraints. So counselors should now provide these services online throughout the country. Anyone from any place or background would be able to talk to desired counselor and get the right suggestions.

Following Procedure can be followed:

- 1) Joint Website of various counselors by a third party
- 2) Individual website by the concerned counselor
- 3) Joint website by the counselors themselves

Joint Website by a Third Party:

A third party professional can make an effort to design a website; where counselors from all parts of the country are asked to register themselves. Following procedure can be used in this business:

- Designing a website by a third party Sending registration requests to counselor`s online.
 - Online registration by the counselors on the website.
 - Advertising the website in schools/colleges/Universities and online.
 - Signup by the students.
 - Students filling their details of previous qualification/background.
 - Choosing the counselor by the clients/suggesting the counselor by the host based on background.
 - Making the payment online.
 - Organizing the voice or video call by the host.
 - Online counseling of the student.
 - Finalizing the career path by the students after counseling of expert.
 - Feedback form filling by the student.
- **Professional and Short Term Courses**
Earlier was the time when once you`re are out of college; your education is complete. But in today`s time education is never over. Everyone keeps on

studying one thing or another for professional and personal growth. A person gets more and more promotions and salary increments as he/she gets further education. In present time after joining corporate/service sector people go for professional and short term courses of 6-12 months. Like short term course on leadership, personality enhancement courses, skill development courses, language speaking courses, computer diplomas, marketing courses etc. But till now the process is that they have to either take leave for 2-6 months or attend the classes on weekends; which sometimes affects their professional and personal lives in a negative way also. Many people want to go for further education/training but cannot go because of time constraint. They do get time to go to college/University to attend the classes and sit in examination. But now Covid-19 has shown the people that everything is possible while sitting at your place. You need to go anywhere. You can attend classes online while sitting with your family members or sitting in the office. Exam and test for performance check can also be conducted online. Yes, some strict measures are required to avoid mal practices. But that can be designed by the experts after deep discussions. We all have seen that during Covid-19; even small kids are attending online classes, appearing in online exams. Earlier National level test like NET/SET/CTET use to be offline; but now these all are being conducted online at various centers in the countries. So this is a great opportunity with the Universities to enlarge their span. They must start providing online education and degrees. It's not that they should shift everything online; but they can open both the options at the same time. Whosoever has time and resources can go to college/University; busy professionals can avail the option of online education. Following options can be considered by the Universities:

- Online classes and examination
- Online classes and offline examination at the University campus at the end of the course
- Online classes and examination at the various centers made by the University for the Convenience of the candidates.

Following procedure can be designed by the Universities to follow online education system:

- Designing the curriculum for online courses---Inviting online application for entrance test.
- Taking offline/online entrance test.
- Announcing the result of selected candidate through E-mails.
- Online/offline counseling procedure and offering the seat to candidate.

- Online/offline submission of courses fee.
- Conduct of online classes.
- Regularly marking the attendance of students who attend online classes.
- Online allocation and submission of projects and assignments.
- Final examination online/offline as per the convenience of candidates.
- Declaration of results.
- Allotment of certificates/diplomas.
- **Architecture Services**

People love staying in beautiful homes, working in well-designed offices and enjoying holidays in 5-star hotels. For this good services of architecture are required as per location and dimensions of space available. Till now people are to see the space dimensions and locality and accordingly architect design the layout for the new building/office/house. But today we are in age of high technology where everything can be shown in computers with the help of Artificial Intelligence. You can fill the dimensions of available space in the software and it will show you various possible combinations of room/kitchen/living areas. But for that you should be computer expert which everyone cannot be. But architect these days are expert in computer graphics. So they can easily design anything for you. Also good architects are not available in small towns and villages. While working online anyone can have best design from the best architect of the country or world. So now trends should be changed; people should be aware of this benefit of online architecture services. Also time and money can be saved. Procedure for online architecture services:

 - Designing of app by the architect/company.
 - Some sample designs of house/office/building are shown in the app.
 - Clients visit the app and see the existing design.
 - Finalizing that they want service from this architect.
 - Filling up the personal details and dimensions details.
 - Making online payments.
 - Video call by the company.
 - Enabling of designing software on the clients' computer for particular time period.
 - Architect shows the various possibilities of house/office/building.
 - Client finalize the design.
 - Deal ended & feedback form filling.
- **Online Coaching and Tuition**

Providing online coaching and tuition is not totally new concept. Many company and individual are successfully running their coaching and tuitions online. Students regularly attend their classes, prepare online assignments and appear in online test series to get ready for competition. But most of these online courses are for competitive exams like NET, JEE, IBPS and other banking test, SSC etc. For regular classes and degree students still visit the coaching/tuition centre physically. These even kids of nursery class are going for tuition daily in the evening after the school. Even today at the time of Covid-19 every one of us can see the children going for tuition. Although some of the parents are not sending their children to tuition; but of us are send them. Because parents have genuine concern that children do not study at home. They are habitual of studying only in front of teacher. Also many dual career couples do not have time to help the children in their studies. That`s y they send them out to some other person to help them in study. So today online tuition/coaching system should not be limited to competitive exams only; individuals and coaching centers should start giving online coaching starting from class 1st.

Yes, it is true that everyone would not be able to switch to online system due resource constraint. But who so ever has resources should provide both online and offline coaching till the time people are facing resource constraint. Once people would get to know about the benefits of online system, they will definitely manage to shift to online system because everybody is worried about the health and safety of family and kids. These days there many applications and softwares are available free of cost which can be used to conduct online classes. For example, Zoom, Google Meet, Youtube etc. Many people have conducted session online and offline to teach people that how to take online class. You can see many such audios and videos on you tube. BYJU`s name everyone must have heard these days. They are providing online classes of every subject with projects and assignments and children like it. So the system of online coaching/tuition should be a normal practice in near future.

- Designing of app or website by the instructor/company.
- Uploading of sample lectures and course structure (fee, timing, syllabus duration) by the host.
- Students see the sample lecture and course structure.
- Students decide to continue with this instructor and make online payment.
- Students join the class.
- Instructor delivers regular lectures and assignments as per plan.
- Course is complete.

- Online test to check performance.
- Revision as per requirement.
- End of classes.

4. Literature Review

Last-mile delivery has become a critical source for market differentiation, motivating retailers to take a position during a myriad of consumer delivery innovations, like buy-online-pickup-in-store, autonomous delivery solutions, lockers, and free delivery upon minimum purchase levels (Lim *et al.*, 2017). Consumers care about last-mile delivery because it offers convenience and adaptability. For these reasons, same-day and on-demand delivery services are gaining traction for groceries (e.g. Deliv Fresh, Instacart), pre-prepared meals (e.g. Sun Basket), and retail purchases (e.g. Dropoff, Amazon Prime Now) (Lopez, 2017). to satisfy customer needs, parcel carriers are increasing investments into urban and automatic distribution hubs (McKevitt, 2017). However, there's a scarcity of understanding on how best to style last-mile delivery models with retailers turning to experimentations that, at times, attract skepticism from industry observers (e.g. Cassidy, 2017). for instance, Sainsbury's, Somerfield, and Asda established innovative pick centres, but closed them down within some years (Ferne *et al.*, 2010). EBay launched its e-Bay Now same-day delivery service in 2012, but in July 2015, it announced the closure of this programme. Google, likewise, opened then closed its two delivery hubs for Google Express in 2013 and 2015, respectively (O'Brien, 2015). The development of those experimental last-mile logistics (LML) models, not surprisingly, created uncertainty within increasingly complicated and fragmented distribution networks. Without sustainable delivery economics, last-mile service provision will struggle to survive (as was the experience of Sainsbury's, Somerfield, Asda, eBay, Google, and Web van) with retailers increasingly challenged to seek out an optimal balance between pricing, consumer expectations for innovative new channels, and repair levels (Lopez, 2017; McKevitt, 2017).

Although several contributions are made within the LML domain, the literature on LML models remains relatively fragmented, thus hindering a comprehensive and holistic understanding of the subject to direct research efforts. Hitherto, existing studies provide limited or no guidance on how contingency variables influence the choice of LML configurations (Galatz *et al.*, 2008; Ferne *et al.*, 2010; Mangiaracina *et al.*, 2015; Lagorio *et al.*, 2016; Savelsbergh and Van Woensel, 2016). Our paper addresses this data deficiency by reviewing the disparate academic literature to capture key contingency and structural variables characterizing the various sorts of last-mile distribution. We then theoretically

establish the connection between these variables thereby providing a design framework for LML models. Our corpus is comprised of 47 papers published in 16 selected peer-reviewed journals during the amount from 2000 to 2017. The review is performed from the standpoint of shops operating LML. As such, some LML research streams are deliberately excluded, including issues regarding public policy, urban traffic regulations, logistics infrastructure, urban sustainability, and environment.

5. Conclusion

E-commerce still represents one of the business methods that take advantage if done the right way, even if the stock market and commodities fell, but E-Commerce still able to survive and receive high transaction. E-commerce has a tremendous opportunity in the course of or business in Malaysia. In addition, it is also to introducing new techniques and styles in a transaction. Use the extensive E-Commerce in the Internet world is actually much better to bring the goodness of the individual or the state. E-Commerce has undeniably become an important part of our society. The successful companies of the future will be those that take E-Commerce seriously, dedicating sufficient resources to its development. E-Commerce is not an IT issue but a whole business undertaking. Companies that use it as a reason for completely re-designing their business processes are likely to reap the greatest benefits. Moreover, E-Commerce is a helpful technology that gives the consumer access to business and companies all over the world.

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